
The Effect of Company Size, Solvency, and Public Accounting Firm Size on Audit Delay (Empirical Study on Agricultural Sector Companies Listed on the IDX 2017-2019)

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ABSTRACT

This study aims to examine and analyze the effect of company size, solvency, and public accounting firm size on audit delay in agricultural companies listed on the IDX from 2017-2019 as partially and simultaneously. This research uses quantitative research using the purposive sampling method. The analysis method in this research study used descriptive statistics, classic assumption tests, hypothesis testing which consisted of simple and multiple linear regression with a significance level of 5%. This research was conducted by selecting research data according to the sample criteria of 15 agricultural companies based on established criteria. The type of data used secondary data obtained from IDX and the company's official website. The results of this research show for the partial test such as company size and public accounting firm size does not affect audit delay, but for solvency affects the audit delay. The result simultaneously tests for company size, solvency, and public accounting firm size tests do not affect audit delay.

1. INTRODUCTION

Financial information is very important for both internal companies and external parties, such as investors, creditors, government, employees, suppliers, and the public (Achmad et al. 2021). The information generated by the company usually annual financial statements. The financial statement is a source of company financial information that is used by external parties in determining a decision. The presentation of financial statements must be following generally accepted financial standards (Febrianto et al. 2022, vol. 3, p.). As a source of information that can influence decisions, financial statements must be reliable, understandable, relevant, and free from material misstatement. Therefore, a financial statement must go through an audit process to ensure that

the financial information presented can be used properly by external and internal parties (Barjono and Hakim 2018).

The companies listed on the stock exchange or categorized as a go-public company should present audited financial statements. The reason for that policy to ensure that companies transparently provide their financial information to stakeholders, especially investors (Hardiyansah et al. 2021). Audited financial statements are considered more reliable because an auditor has checked and confirmed that the information presented has passed the audit test (Agustin et al. 2021). So that the role of professionalism is also very important in ensuring the reliability of financial reports.

As already stated, the financial statements must be relevant, those refer to the reaction of a party when the audited financial

statements are published (Singleton 2018). Therefore, for the information presented in the financial statements to have good relevance, an audited financial report must be presented on time. Any delay in the publication of financial reports can cause the report to lose the relevancy of information. This is one of the bad things because audited financial statements contain a variety of important information such as the level of company profits. Profit information is something that many investors consider in determining whether to invest or not (Khasanah et al. 2021). If an investor has decided to invest in a company based on the information he has, it means that the company's shares will increase (Aduroh and Paramu 2021).

The regulations of the deadline publication of audited financial statements do not make all public companies listed on the capital market always obedient to that regulation, some of companies always late to submit their financial statements (Putra and Prabowo 2019). In 2020 the IDX reported that there were 80 listed companies late in submitted their annual audited financial statements, for the year ended 31 December 2019. Meanwhile, in July 2018 the IDX suspended 10 listed companies that had not submitted their financial statements which ended on December 31st 2018 and they should pay a fine of IDR 150 million (Hardiyansah et al. 2021).

The duration of time required by the auditor to perform an audit starting from the closing date of the company's annual book until the auditor's report is signed is called audit delay. The longer duration of time required by the auditor to perform auditing, the longer the audit delay will be (Wijaya et al. 2021).

Many factors can affect audit delays, such as profitability, company size, solvency, auditor opinion, public accounting firm size, etc. In this study, the researcher only used company size, solvency, and public accounting firm size as variables (Meita et al. 2020). The first factor that can affect audit delay is company size. Research conducted by Lestari and Putu (2017) shows that there is no effect of company size on audit delay. This is because sooner or later the results of the audit financial statements depend on the performance of the auditors, even though the company has large or small assets, the auditor still professionally completes the audit report. While the research conduct by Clarisa and Pangerapan (2019) company size has a significant effect on audit delay, this is because the larger the size of

the company has more audit procedures to be performed. Large companies have wider activities and a high volume of activities, also because of the higher number of transactions within the company then the complexity of the transaction increases (Purnamawati et al. 2019).

Then the second factor that affects audit delay is solvency. Research conducted by Lestari and Putu (Lestari and Putu 2017) states that solvency does not affect the audit delay of manufacturing companies listed on the IDX from 2012-2015 it is because the company's ability to pay off its debts does not affect audit delay. It is different from the research results from Apriyana and Rahmawati (2017) stated that solvency has a significant effect on audit delay.

The last factor that affects audit delay is the public accounting firm size which is classified into large and small, for large public accounting, such as public accounting affiliated with big four public accounting (Novitasari et al. 2019). While the small public accounting is local public accounting in Indonesia or out from the big four. The results of the research (Candraningtyas et al. 2017) show that the public accounting size has a significant negative effect on audit delay because the big four public accounting usually maintains more quality and more experienced so they might be work more professionally than non the big four auditors. The big four public accounting will work more effectively and efficiently so that it will be faster in submitting audited reports (Eriandani and Winarno 2021).

There are many problems of delays in the submission of audited financial statements of companies on IDX and there are still inconsistent research results that are suspected to be the factors that affect the delays in the submission of audited financial statements (Wasito et al. 2019). So, in this case author choosing the title of this article as "*The Effect of Company Size, Solvency, and Public Accounting Firm Size to Audit Delay (Empirical Study on Agricultural Sector Companies Listed on the IDX 2017-2019)*"

2. THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK AND HYPOTHESES

The Signaling Theory

Signaling theory is included in the pragmatic accounting theory which focuses on the effect of information on changes in the behavior of information users. One of the information that provides a signal is the announcement of information in the financial

statements made by an issuer (Gomulya and Mishina 2017). This announcement usually affects the ups and downs of the securities of the issuing company when the announcement is made to the public. The signaling theory states that good quality companies will deliberately give signals to the market, thus the market is expected to differentiate between good and bad quality companies (Kustono 2020). To make the signal work effective, the information must be able to understand by the user in the capital market also have a good perceived, and not easily imitated by companies with poor quality (Dewangga and Laksito 2015).

Audit Delay

Audit delay or Audit report lag is the period for completion of the annual financial report audit from the closing of the company's books to the date stated in the independent auditor's report (Halim 2000). The factors that influence audit delay are company size, solvency, audit tenure, public accounting firm size, auditor switch, and profitability, company age (Mas'ud 2016).

Development of Hypotheses

1. The Effect of Company Size on Audit Delay

Company size is a large/small scale company which is usually determined by the amount of wealth owned and the size of the company's transactions. (Wasito et al. 2019) The relationship between company size and audit delay is that when a company belongs to a large group of companies, the audit process carried out by the auditor will be longer and more complicated. this is because large companies tend to have more and more complicated transactions, so it takes longer than auditing small companies. (Barjono and Hakim 2018) Based on research conducted by Apriyana and Rahmawati (Apriyana and Rahmawati 2017) company size influences audit delay, while Lestari and Putu (Lestari and Putu 2017) and Sari et al. (2014) their research shows that company size does not affect audit delay. Based on this statement, the hypothesis proposed in this study:

H1: Firm size has a negative effect on audit delay

2. The Effect of Solvency on Audit Delay

Solvency is the level of a company's ability to meet obligations, both short and long term. One of the calculations of solvability is the Debt to Asset Ratio (DAR), where if the DAR

level is high it indicates the high financial risk the company has. (Nur Izzatika et al. 2020) This measurement greatly influences the user's decision and the effect will show in securities price in the capital market. A high solvency ratio will give bad news to the company because of the high financial risk due to difficulties in paying off its obligations and will be affect the sustainability of company. Apriyana and Rahmawati (Apriyana and Rahmawati 2017) shows the effect of solvency on audit delay. Meanwhile, research by Clarisa and Pangerapan (Clarisa and Pangerapan 2019) and Barjono and Hakim (2018) states that solvency does not affect audit delay. Based on the explanation above, the hypothesis is formulated: H2: Solvency has a positive effect on audit delay.

3. The Effect of Public Accounting Firm Size on Audit Delay

A large public accounting size is considered to have a shorter period for the auditing process, this is because a large public accounting size has a lot and better resources than a small public accounting size. Besides, the good reputation of the Public Accounting Firm will carry out a more efficient audit process and the audited financial information is under the fairness of a company's financial statements. (Kuncorowati et al. 2021) So that the indicator of public accounting size uses the classification of Public Accounting Firms affiliated with the Big Four Worldwide Accounting Firm (big4) and outside the big4. This is consistent with the statement that large public accounting firms have more resources and quality than small public accounting firms. Clarisa and Pangerapan (Clarisa and Pangerapan 2019) and Apriyana and Rahmawati (Apriyana and Rahmawati 2017) state in their research that there is an effect of public accounting size on audit delay. Meanwhile, Kartika (2009) shows that public accounting size does not affect audit delay. Based on the description above, the hypothesis formulation is:

H3: Public accounting size has a negative effect on audit delay.

4. The Effect of Company Firm Size, Solvency and Public Accounting Size on Audit Delay

Simultaneous testing of audit delay factors is intended to determine whether these factors together affect the audit process period. Research conducted by Saemargani and Mustikawati (2015) shows that the simultaneous

testing of audit delay factors affects audit delay. H4: Company size, solvency, and public

Therefore, the hypothesis formulated is: accounting size simultaneously effect on audit delay

Figure 1. Research Model

3. RESEARCH METHOD

This type of research is quantitative research that tests using variables factor that affects the audit delay. Sugiyono (2011) defines quantitative research as a research method based on the philosophy of positivism, used to examine specific populations or samples, sampling techniques that are generally carried out randomly, data collection using research instruments, quantitative/statistical data analysis with the aim of test the hypothesis that has been set. The process of testing and measuring data in this research uses the IBM SPSS Statistics version 23 tool (Trihendradi 2013). The population in this study were agricultural sector companies listed on the IDX for the period 2017 - 2019. The sample was taken by purposive sampling method and 15 companies met the criteria from 24 listed agricultural companies. The analysis method in this research study used descriptive statistics and classic assumption tests, the hypothesis testing consisted of simple and multiple linear regression with a significance level of 5%.

4. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Descriptive Statistic

In this study, descriptive statistics provide a description or description of data consisting of the average (mean), maximum, and minimum values.

Table 1. Statistical Descriptive Test Result

Variable	N	Min.	Max.	Mean
Company Size	45	26.62	31.18	29.62

Solvency	45	0.11	1.65	0.53
Public accounting size	45	0	1	0.58
Audit Delay	45	50	149	81.87

Sources: Output of SPSS

Normality Test

The results of normality testing of the four variables with statistical tests using the One-Sample Kolmogorov-Smirnov Test are as follows:

Table 2. Normality Test Result

Sig.	Interpretation
0.65	Normal

Sources: Output of SPSS

Based on the result above, the significance value is greater than the value of the normality requirement of (0.65 > 0.05), so it can be concluded that the data used in this research regression model are normally distributed.

Heteroscedasticity Test

Table 3. Heteroscedasticity Test Result

Variable	Sig.	Interpretation
Company Size	0.577	There is no heteroscedasticity
Solvency	0.137	There is no heteroscedasticity
Public Accounting Size	0.478	There is no heteroscedasticity

Sources: Output of SPSS

Based on the test results data above, the significance value of each independent variable is greater than 0.05 as the minimal significance level. So, it can be concluded that heteroscedasticity does not occur in this regression model.

Multicollinearity Test

Table 4. Multicollinearity Test Result

Variable	Tolerance	VIF	Interpretation
Firm Size	0.698	1.432	There is no multicollinearity
Solvability	0.714	1.400	There is no multicollinearity
KAP Size	0.580	1.724	There is no multicollinearity

Sources: Output of SPSS

Based on the results test above, it can be seen that each independent variable has a tolerance value > 10% and a VIF value < 10, so it can be concluded that all independent variable data do not have multicollinearity indication in this regression model.

Autocorrelation Test

Table 5. Autocorrelation Test Result

Durbin-Watson	Interpretation
1.857	There is no autocorrelation

Sources: Output of SPSS

Based on the results of the test above, Durbin Watson (DW) value obtained is 1,857 greater than the upper limit (du) 1.6662 and less than (4-du) or $4 - 1.6662 = 2.3338$, then the equation $dU < dW < 4 - dU$ is $1.6662 < 1.857 < 2.3338$ So it can be concluded that in this regression model there is no autocorrelation.

Analysis Test Result

Table 5. Analysis Test Result

Simple Linear Regression Analysis Test Result				
Variable	Coeff. Regression	t _{count}	R ²	Sig.
Firm Size	-0.013	-0.867	0.017	0.391
Solvability	0.127	2.125	0.095	0.039
KAP Size	-0.069	-1.990	0.084	0.053

Multiple Linear Regression Analysis Test Result

Variable	Coeff. Regression	F _{count}	Adj. R ²	Sig.
Firm Size	-0.010			
Solvability	0.108	2.095	0.069	0.116
KAP Size	-0.032			

Sources: Output of SPSS

Effect Company Size on Audit Delay

The first hypothesis in this study, there is a negative effect on the company size on audit delay. The results of the calculation of simple linear regression using the SPSS tool based on Table 6 obtained a regression coefficient of -0.013 and a probability of 0.391. The probability is greater than 0.05, so it can be concluded that company size has no significant negative effect on audit delay. This result is in line with research conducted by Lestari and Putu (Lestari and Putu 2017) which states that company size does not affect audit delay.

The conclusion about company size does not affect audit delay in the agricultural sector, this means that auditors in completing their obligation to audit do not see the size of a company. Auditors in this case carry out professionalism in providing services for both large and small companies. Even though large companies tend to have more wealth and transactions that require a more complex testing process, this does not make auditors carry out their duties unprofessional. This is also due to the time limit given by BAPEPAM in the submission of audited financial statements, so the auditor will also consider completing the audit process immediately. Also, auditors must be able to give confidence to the company if they can complete the audit process as quickly as possible so that the company continues to use its audit services.

Effect Solvency on Audit Delay

Solvency is important for the assessment of stakeholders because this level greatly affects the level of risk a company has. The second hypothesis in this study is there is a positive effect of solvency on audit delay. Testing data through simple regression shows that the regression coefficient value is 0.127 and the probability value is 0.039 where the value meets the critical requirements, which is greater than 0.05, so the conclusion is H2 accepted which is solvency as measured by Debt to Asset Ratio (DAR) has a significant positive effect on the audit delay.

The results of this study are in line with research from Apriyana and Rahmawati (Apriyana and Rahmawati 2017) which also has the same result that there is a significant effect of solvency on audit delay. Even though we used different populations, the result can be concluded that the higher solvency level of the company, the longer time needed auditor to carry out the audit process and causing a longer audit delay. This is because the debt auditing process requires a longer check, especially if a company that has a high level of solvency borrows from different and many debtholders.

Effect Public Accounting Firm Size on Audit Delay

The third hypothesis for this study is that the public accounting firm size has a negative effect on audit delay. From the results testing using the SPSS tool, the regression coefficient value of -0.069 and for the probability value of 0.053 which is still classified as greater than the critical requirement of 0.05 so that H1 is rejected and the conclusion that there is no significant negative effect of public accounting firm size on audit delay.

The results of this study imply that although the size of the public accounting firm size large or small, there is no effect on how long the auditing period auditor's needed. So, this indicates that auditors from both small and large public accounting firm size will try to minimize a longer audit delay. Then also, although a larger public accounting firm size has relatively more resources, the results of research on companies in the agricultural sector do not have a very significant effect on audit delay.

Effect Company Size, Solvency, Public Accounting Firm Size on Audit Delay

The results of the fourth hypothesis test using multiple linear regression tests, namely company size, solvency, and public accounting firm size simultaneously do not affect audit delay in agricultural companies listed on IDX 2017-2019. The evidence of the test results using the SPSS tool that the F significance 0.116, which exceeds the critical probability value of 0.05 and the F count value is smaller than F-table, the equation is $F \text{ count} < F \text{ table}$ ($2.095 < 2.83$).

The size of the company is usually measured by the company's total assets and simplified using natural logarithms. Large companies usually have a large level of sales,

total assets, and equity as well. On the other hand, a relatively small company must also have smaller total assets, sales, and equity. The level of solvency also indicates the company's risk, which is considered to have an impact on the uncertainty of the company's sustainability and share prices. If the level of solvency of a company is high, the risk of failure of the company to pay off the loan will be high, and vice versa. Then the public accounting firm sizes are grouped into big four and non-big four, where the big four is considered to have more resources and is competent so that it reduces audit delay. However, in the results of research on companies in the agricultural sector, the three factors that can affect audit delay do not show a simultaneous effect.

5. CONCLUSION, IMPLICATION, SUGGESTION, AND LIMITATIONS

Summary of research in the previous chapter can be concluded that the partial hypothesis test with simple linear regression test shows that company size (X1) and public accounting firm size (X2) does not effect on audit delay, but for solvency (X3) has a significant positive effect on audit delay. Furthermore, the results of the fourth hypothesis test (H4) through multiple linear regression show that firm size, solvency, and size of KAP on audit delay do not meet the regression requirements so that there is no simultaneous effect on audit delay.

The following are some of the limitations in this study which consist of:

1. The research sample focuses on companies in the agricultural sector listed on IDX there are not as many as other sector companies and only 15 out of the total 24 agricultural sector companies meet the criteria so the research results obtained are less than optimal.
2. The study period carried out in this research is only three years using secondary data, so the result might not match in the ground and some other factors that not include in this research might also affect audit delay.

Some suggestions that might be considered for advanced research on audit delay, including the following:

1. use the research samples that are different from those conducted by previous researchers, so that the results can be reinforced by research that has been done.
2. use or add other variables than that were used in this study and also use a population that

can represent the company as a whole so that the results will be more accurate.

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